

ANALISIS KETERAMPILAN MENULIS MELALUI PROYEK PENGUATAN PROFIL PELAJAR PANCASILA DI SMP

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Abstrak

Tujuan penelitian untuk mengetahui hasil pembelajaran keterampilan menulis melalui proyek profil pelajar Pancasila di SMP Al-Fityan Kubu Raya, Kalimantan Barat. Metode penelitian yang digunakan adalah deskriptif kualitatif. Responden penelitian berjumlah 26 peserta didik yang berasal dari kelas VII SMP Al-Fityan Kubu Raya. Teknik pengumpulan data dilakukan dengan observasi dan tes. Alat pengumpulan data menggunakan lembar observasi dan tes *essay*. Teknik analisis data menggunakan model Miles and Huberman. Berdasarkan hasil penelitian disimpulkan bahwa keterampilan menulis peserta didik kelas VII SMP Al-Fityan Kubu Raya melalui proyek penguatan profil pelajar Pancasila dengan tema gaya hidup berkelanjutan judul “Sampahku, tanggung jawabku” termasuk dalam kategori sangat baik.

Kata Kunci: keterampilan menulis; profil pelajar Pancasila; gaya hidup berkelanjutan.

Abstract

The research aimed to determine the learning outcomes of writing skills through the Pancasila student profile project at Al-Fityan Kubu Raya Junior High School, West Kalimantan. The research method used descriptive qualitative. The research respondents were 26 students from class VII SMP Al-Fityan Kubu Raya. Data collection techniques were carried out by observation and tests. Data collection tools used observation sheets and essay tests. The data analysis technique used the Miles and Huberman model. Based on the results of the research, it can be concluded that the writing skills of seventh grade students of SMP Al-Fityan Kubu Raya through a project to strengthen the profile of Pancasila students with the theme of a sustainable lifestyle "My trash, my responsibility" was included in the very good category.

Keywords: writing skills; Pancasila student profiles; sustainable lifestyle.